

SUMBERS – SUMS OF UPS AND DOWNS

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Abstract

A sumner is a sum of ups, downs and star. We provide a simplification rule that can determine whether a game G is a sumner or not, and if it is, determine the exact sumner of G from its left and right options, G^L and G^R . Once one knows a game is a sumner, the outcome of the game can be determined by a simple rule.

1. Introduction

We are concerned with combinatorial games and follow the notations and conventions of *Winning Ways* [1]. A game G is an ordered pair of sets of games,

$$G = \{G^L | G^R\},$$

where G^L and G^R are called the left and right options of G . We assume the readers are familiar with the *birthdays* [2] of games, and say a game is *simpler* if it was *born* earlier. The simplest game is the game 0, defined as

$$0 = \{ | \}.$$

The following are the basic definitions of combinatorial games:

$$-G = \{-G^R | -G^L\}.$$

$$G \geq H \text{ iff no element in } G^R \leq H.$$

$$G \leq H \text{ iff no element in } G^L \geq H.$$

$$G = H \text{ iff } G \geq H \text{ and } G \leq H.$$

$$G + H = \{G^L + H, G + H^L | G^R + H, G + H^R\}.$$

These few lines already define a group with a very rich structure. The properties of zero, negation, order, equality and addition, can be proven to have the *usual* [1][2] behaviors.

There is a natural interpretation of the order defined above. Consider a game G played by two players, L and R , who move alternatively. The player who makes the last legal move is the winner. The outcome of the game can be describe as:

$$\begin{aligned} G \geq 0, & \text{ if } R \text{ cannot win the game playing first,} \\ G \leq 0, & \text{ if } L \text{ cannot win the game playing first,} \\ G = 0, & \text{ if the first player cannot win the game, and} \\ G \not\geq H \text{ and } G \not\leq H, & \text{ if the first player can win the game.} \end{aligned}$$

To ease the discussion, we include the following definitions.

$$\begin{aligned} G \parallel H & \text{ iff } G \not\geq H \text{ and } G \not\leq H, \\ G > H & \text{ iff } G \geq H \text{ and } G \neq H, \\ G < H & \text{ iff } G \leq H \text{ and } G \neq H, \\ G \mid > H & \text{ iff } G \not\leq H, \\ G < \mid H & \text{ iff } G \not\geq H. \end{aligned}$$

For any game G , the outcome is in one of the four cases: $G > 0$, $G < 0$, $G = 0$, or $G \parallel 0$.

In general, it is not an easy task to determine the outcome of a complex game. We are interested in subgroups of games with the following properties:

1. There exists a simple rule to determine the outcome of any game in the subgroup.
2. There exists a simplification rule that can simplify games in the subgroup.

For examples, *numbers* [2] and *nimbers* [3] are well known subgroups with the above properties. The *simplest number rule* [2] and the *minimal excluded rule* [4] can simplify numbers and nimbers respectively.

In this article, we study another subgroup of games called *sumeurs*. Sumeurs also have the properties mentioned above. The rest of this article is organized as follows. In section 2, we introduce the constituting elements of a sumber : ups, downs and star. We define the *minimum cut* of a sumber and the *critical section* of a game whose options are sumbers. The critical section plays an important role in determining whether a game is a sumber or not. In section 3, we present the major result for single-option games, together with the proofs. In section 4, the result is extended to cover multi-option games. Examples are provided in section 5.

2. Sumbers

2.1 Ups and Downs

For any number d , define

$$\uparrow(d) = \{\uparrow(d^L), *|*, \uparrow(d^R)\}$$

where $*$ = $\{0|0\}$ (pronounced *star*). When $d = 0$, we have

$$\uparrow(0) = \{*\} = 0.$$

By simple induction, one can show that, for any number d ,

$$\uparrow(-d) = \{\uparrow(-d^R), *|*, \uparrow(-d^L)\} = \{-\uparrow(d^R), *|*, -\uparrow(d^L)\} = -\uparrow(d).$$

Each $\uparrow(d)$, $d > 0$, is called an *up* and has atomic weight 1 [2] (chapter 16, page 218). The negation of an up is called a *down*. The number d is called the *order* of $\uparrow(d)$.

We use the notation $n.\uparrow(d)$ to denote the sum of n copies of $\uparrow(d)$:

$$0.\uparrow(d) = 0$$

$$n.\uparrow(d) = (n - 1).\uparrow(d) + \uparrow(d), n > 0.$$

The ups defined above have the following properties:

Proposition 1: $\uparrow(d_2) > \uparrow(d_1)$, for all $d_2 > d_1$.

Proof: We prove by induction. When $d_1 = 0$, the claim is clearly true. Otherwise, suppose the claim is true for simpler games. Since $d_2 > d_1$, we have $d_2 > d_1^L$ and $d_2^R > d_1$. By induction hypothesis, we have $\uparrow(d_2) > \uparrow(d_1^L)$ and $\uparrow(d_2^R) > \uparrow(d_1)$. This implies R cannot win the game $\uparrow(d_2) - \uparrow(d_1)$ playing first. Thus $\uparrow(d_2) > \uparrow(d_1)$. \square

Proposition 2: $\uparrow(d_2) + \uparrow(d_2) - \uparrow(d_1) + * > 0$, for all $d_2 > d_1 > 0$.

Proof: Consider the game $G = \uparrow(d_2) + \uparrow(d_2) - \uparrow(d_1) + *$. L can win G by moving to $\uparrow(d_2) + \uparrow(d_2)$. R cannot win G by moving to $\uparrow(d_2^R) + \uparrow(d_2) - \uparrow(d_1) + *$, $\uparrow(d_2) - \uparrow(d_1)$, $\uparrow(d_2) + \uparrow(d_2) - \uparrow(d_1^L) + *$, $\uparrow(d_2) + \uparrow(d_2)$, $\uparrow(d_2) + \uparrow(d_2) - \uparrow(d_1)$. Thus $\uparrow(d_2) + \uparrow(d_2) - \uparrow(d_1) + * > 0$. \square

Proposition 3: $\uparrow(d_2) - \uparrow(d_1) > n.(\uparrow(d_3) - \uparrow(d_2))$, for all $d_3 > d_2 > d_1 > 0$ and $n \geq 0$.

Proof: We prove by induction on n . When $n = 0$, the claim is clearly true. Otherwise, suppose the claim is true when $n = k$. Let d be a number such that $d_2 > d > d_1$. By induction hypothesis, we have $\uparrow(d_2) - \uparrow(d) > k.(\uparrow(d_3) - \uparrow(d_2))$ and $\uparrow(d) - \uparrow(d_1) > \uparrow(d_2) - \uparrow(d) > \uparrow(d_3) - \uparrow(d_2)$. Thus $\uparrow(d_2) - \uparrow(d_1) > (k + 1).(\uparrow(d_3) - \uparrow(d_2))$. \square

A sum of ups, downs and star is called a *sumber*. A sumber S can be written in the standard form:

$$S = s_0 \cdot * + \sum_{k=1,n} s_k \cdot \uparrow (d_k),$$

where $s_0 = 0$ or 1 , $s_k \neq 0, 0 < k \leq n$ and $0 < d_k < d_{k+1}, 0 < k < n$.

$\sum_{k=1,n} s_k$ is called the *net weight* of S .

Sumbers are closed under addition. Conway first found this interesting subgroup of games. He also found a rule [2](theorem 88, page 194) similar to the theorem below to determine the outcome of a sumber.

Theorem 1: *Sumber outcome rule.* Let S be a sumber in the above standard form.

- $S > 0$ if and only if $(\sum_{k=1,n} s_k > s_0)$ or $(\sum_{k=1,n} s_k = s_0$ and $s_1 < 0)$.
- $S < 0$ if and only if $-S > 0$
- $S = 0$ if and only if $n = 0$ and $s_0 = 0$.
- $S \mid 0$, otherwise.

Proof: We prove the *if* part of the first case. The rest is trivial once the first case been proven. If $\sum_{k=1,n} s_k > s_0$, let d be a number such that $d_1 > d > 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} S &= s_0 \cdot * + \sum_{k=1,n} s_k \cdot \uparrow (d_k) \\ &> s_0 \cdot * + \sum_{k=1,n} |s_k| \cdot (\uparrow (d_1) - \uparrow (d_n)) + \sum_{k=1,n} s_k \cdot \uparrow (d_1) \\ &> s_0 \cdot * + \uparrow (d) - \uparrow (d_1) + (s_0 + 1) \cdot \uparrow (d_1) \\ &= s_0 \cdot * + \uparrow (d) + s_0 \cdot \uparrow (d_1) > 0. \end{aligned}$$

If $\sum_{k=1,n} s_k = s_0$ and $s_1 < 0$, let d be a number such that $d_2 > d > d_1$, then

$$\begin{aligned} S &= s_0 \cdot * + \sum_{k=1,n} s_k \cdot \uparrow (d_k) \\ &> s_0 \cdot * + \sum_{k=2,n} |s_k| \cdot (\uparrow (d_2) - \uparrow (d_n)) + \sum_{k=2,n} s_k \cdot \uparrow (d_2) + s_1 \cdot \uparrow (d_1) \\ &> s_0 \cdot * + \uparrow (d) - \uparrow (d_2) + (s_0 - s_1) \cdot \uparrow (d_2) + s_1 \cdot \uparrow (d_1) \\ &> s_0 \cdot * + \uparrow (d) + s_0 \cdot \uparrow (d_2) - \uparrow (d_1) > 0. \end{aligned}$$

□

2.2. Minimum Cut and Critical Section

Definition 1: *Cut of a sumber.* Let S be a sumber written in the standard form:

$$S = s_0 \cdot * + \sum_{k=1, n} s_k \cdot \uparrow (d_k),$$

where $s_0 = 0$ or 1 , $s_k \neq 0$, $0 < k \leq n$ and $0 < d_k < d_{k+1}$, $0 < k < n$.

For $m \in \{0, d_k : 1 \leq k \leq n\}$, define

$$S^m = \sum_{k=1, n; d_k \geq m} s_k \cdot \uparrow (d_k) - \sum_{k=1, n; d_k < m} s_k \cdot \uparrow (m).$$

We say S has a *cut* at m if $S^m \leq 0$.

Example 1: Consider the sumber $S = 4 \cdot \uparrow (1) - 2 \cdot \uparrow (2) + \uparrow (3) + \uparrow (5) - \uparrow (6)$.

$$\begin{array}{l} S^0 = 4 \cdot \uparrow (1) - 2 \cdot \uparrow (2) + \uparrow (3) + \uparrow (5) - \uparrow (6) \quad - 3 \cdot \uparrow (0) > 0, \\ S^1 = 4 \cdot \uparrow (1) - 2 \cdot \uparrow (2) + \uparrow (3) + \uparrow (5) - \uparrow (6) \quad - 3 \cdot \uparrow (1) < 0, \\ S^2 = \quad \quad \quad - 2 \cdot \uparrow (2) + \uparrow (3) + \uparrow (5) - \uparrow (6) \quad + 1 \cdot \uparrow (2) > 0, \\ S^3 = \quad \quad \quad \quad \quad \uparrow (3) + \uparrow (5) - \uparrow (6) \quad - 1 \cdot \uparrow (3) < 0, \\ S^5 = \quad \quad \quad \quad \quad \quad \uparrow (5) - \uparrow (6) \quad + 0 \cdot \uparrow (5) < 0, \\ S^6 = \quad \quad \quad \quad \quad \quad \quad \quad - \uparrow (6) \quad + 1 \cdot \uparrow (6) = 0. \end{array}$$

Thus, S has cuts at 1, 3, 5 and 6. □

We only concerned with the *minimum cut*: the smallest number in $\{0, d_k : 1 \leq k \leq n\}$ which is a cut. When S is a sumber, and m is the minimum cut of S , we call S^m the *upper section* and $S_m = S - S^m$ the *lower section* of S .

Example 2: Consider the sumber $S = 4 \cdot \uparrow (1) - 2 \cdot \uparrow (2) + \uparrow (3) + \uparrow (5) - \uparrow (6)$.

From example 1, we know S has cuts at 1, 3, 5 and 6. The minimum cut of S is at 1. The upper section of S is $S^1 = \uparrow (1) - 2 \cdot \uparrow (2) + \uparrow (3) + \uparrow (5) - \uparrow (6)$, and the lower section is $S_1 = 3 \cdot \uparrow (1)$. □

Definition 2: *Critical section of $\{A|B\}$.* Let A, B be two sumbres, define

$$X(A|B) = \{x \geq m : A - B_m + * < | \uparrow (x) < | B^m + *, m \text{ is the minimum cut of } B\}.$$

$X(A|B)$ is called the *critical section* of the game $\{A|B\}$.

The calculation of $X(A|B)$ involves solving inequalities of sumbres. Theorem 1 can help in solving these inequalities.

Example 3: Consider the game $\{0|S\} = \{0 \mid 4. \uparrow(1) - 2. \uparrow(2) + \uparrow(3) + \uparrow(5) - \uparrow(6)\}$.

From example 2, we know the minimum cut of S is at 1.

$$\begin{aligned} X(0|S) &= \{x \geq 1 : 0 - S_1 + * < \mid \uparrow(x) < \mid S^1 + *\} \\ &= \{x \geq 1 : -3. \uparrow(1) + * < \mid \uparrow(x) < \mid \uparrow(1) - 2. \uparrow(2) + \uparrow(3) + \uparrow(5) - \uparrow(6) + *\} \\ &= \{1\}. \end{aligned}$$

□

One of the interesting results about ups is the following up-star equality [2]:

$$\{0 \mid \uparrow(1)\} = \uparrow(1) + \uparrow(1) + *.$$

The interesting point is that certain games can be decomposed as sums of ups, downs and star.

Kao [5] also designed a game played on a number of heaps of colored counters. Each counter is colored either black or white. Left and Right move alternatively and their legal moves are different:

- When it is L 's turn to move, he can choose any one of the heaps and repeatedly removes the top counter of that heap until either he removed a white counter or the heap has become empty.
- When it is R 's turn to move, he can choose any one of the heaps and repeatedly removes the top counter of that heap until either he removed a black counter or the heap has become empty.

The player who remove the last counter is the winner. Kao [5] found that each of the colored heaps can be decomposed as a sum of ups, downs and star.

These exciting results raise the questions: *what is the general rule that a game can be decomposed as a sum of ups, downs and star? Can we obtain a result similar to the simplest number rule for numbers or the minimal excluded value rule for nimbers?* As we shall see in the next section, the answer is yes and $X(A|B)$ plays an important role in determining whether $\{A|B\}$ is a sumner or not.

3. Sumner Simplification Rule

If A and B are sumners then the following rule can determine whether $\{A|B\}$ is a sumner or not.

Theorem 2: *Sumber simplification rule* (single-option games).

Let A, B be two numbers.

1. If $A < | 0$ and $B | > 0$ then $\{A|B\} = 0$.
2. Otherwise, either $A \geq 0$ or $B \leq 0$. Without loss of generality, we may assume $A \geq 0$ and the net weight of $A + B$ is greater than or equal to 0 (otherwise, apply this rule to $-\{A|B\}$). By assumption, the net weight of B is greater than or equal to -1 (otherwise, $\{A|B\}$ is not a sumber).
 - (a) If B has non-negative net weight then $\{A|B\}$ is a sumber if and only if $X(A|B)$ is not empty.
 - (b) If B has net weight -1 and $B || 0$ then $\{A|B\}$ is a sumber if and only if $X(A|B)$ is not empty.
 - (c) Otherwise, B has net weight -1 , and $B < 0$. If $A || *$ and $B || *$, then $\{A|B\} = *$.
 - (d) Otherwise, B has net weight -1 , either $A > *$ or $B < *$. Without loss of generality, we may assume $A > *$ (otherwise, apply this rule to $-\{A|B\}$). $\{A|B\}$ is a sumber if and only if $X(A|B)$ is not empty.

In cases 2(a), 2(b), and 2(d), If $\{A|B\}$ is a sumber then $\{A|B\} = B_m + ** \uparrow (p)$ where m is the minimum cut of B and p is the simplest number in $X(A|B)$.

The proofs for the above cases are provided in propositions 4, 5, and 6.

Lemma 1: *If B is a sumber with non-negative net weight and $m \geq 0$ is the minimum cut of B , then, whenever L removes a negative term from B_m , R can find a higher or equal order positive term from the remaining sum to remove.*

Proof: When $m = 0$, since B has non-negative net weight, we have either $B_m = 0$ or $B_m = *$. In either case, there is no negative term in B_m and the claim is obviously true.

When $m > 0$, we prove the claim by contradiction. Consider the game B_m . Suppose, after some pair(s) of moves, L chooses $-\uparrow (b)$ in the remaining sum and the most positive term left is $\uparrow (a)$, $0 < a < b < m$. By assumption, B_m must be of the form:

$$B_m = (\text{terms with order } \leq a) + \uparrow (a) - \uparrow (b) + (\text{terms with order } \geq b, \text{ net weight } = 0).$$

But this implies $a < m$ is a cut of B and m is not the minimum cut, a contradiction. \square

Lemma 2: *If B is a sumber with non-negative net weight, and $m > 0$ is the minimum cut of B , then $\{0|B\} - B_m + \uparrow (m) - \uparrow (n) \geq 0$, for all $n < m$.*

Proof: It is sufficient to show that L cannot win the sum $S = \{-B | 0\} + B_m - \uparrow (m) + \uparrow (n)$. Without loss of generality, we may assume n is a number greater than the order of the most negative term in B_m .

1. L cannot win S by choosing the $\{-B \mid 0\}$ option, because $-B + B_m - \uparrow(m) + \uparrow(n) = -B^m - \uparrow(m) + \uparrow(n) < 0$ (the sum has net weight 0, without $*$, and the smallest term, $\uparrow(n)$, is positive,).
2. L cannot win S by choosing any negative term from $B_m - \uparrow(m) + \uparrow(n)$, because, by lemma 1, whenever L removes a negative term from $B_m - \uparrow(m) + \uparrow(n)$, R can find a higher or equal order positive term from the remaining sum to remove. ($B_m - \uparrow(m) + \uparrow(n)$ has non-negative net weight and it equals its lower section.)
3. L cannot win S by choosing any positive term from $B_m - \uparrow(m) + \uparrow(n)$. From *atomic weight calculus* [1], we know the atomic weight of $\{0 \mid B\}$ equals -1 , 0 or $[1 + \text{the atomic weight of } B]$, depending on $\{0 \mid B\}$ is less than, confused with, or greater than the remote star. Since B has non-negative atomic weight and $m > 0$, we know $B \not\leq 0$, and $B \not\leq *$, thus $\{0 \mid B\} > 0$ and $\{0 \mid B\} > *$, the atomic weight of $\{0 \mid B\}$ must equals $[1 + \text{the atomic weight of } B]$. This implies the atomic weight of S is -1 . So, L cannot win S by choosing some positive term from $B_m - \uparrow(m) + \uparrow(n)$.

From 1, 2 and 3, we know L cannot win S . □

Lemma 3: *If $A \geq 0$ is a sumner, B is a sumner with non-negative net weight, $m \geq 0$ is the minimum cut of B , then $\{A \mid B\} - B_m + * - \uparrow(n) > 0$, for all $n < m$.*

Proof: Consider the sum $S = \{A \mid B\} - B_m + * - \uparrow(n)$.

When $m = 0$, since B has non-negative net weight, we have either $B_m = 0$ or $B_m = *$. Note that in this case $n < 0$. If $B_m = 0$ then $S = \{A \mid B^m\} + * - \uparrow(n) > 0$. If $B_m = *$ then $S = \{A \mid B^m + *\} - \uparrow(n) > 0$. In either case, we have $S > 0$.

When $m > 0$, we need to show that L can and R cannot win S . Without loss of generality, we may assume n is a number greater than the order of the most negative term in B_m . L can win S by choosing the $-\uparrow(m)$ term in $-B_m$, because, after L 's move, the sum becomes $\{A \mid B\} - B_m + \uparrow(m) - \uparrow(n) \geq \{0 \mid B\} - B_m + \uparrow(m) - \uparrow(n) \geq 0$ (by lemma 2). R cannot win S by choosing the $\{A \mid B\}$ option, because, after R 's move, the sum becomes $B - B_m + * - \uparrow(n) \mid 0$ (there exists $*$, net weight = -1 , and the least order term is negative). R cannot win S by choosing any positive term from $-B_m$, because, by lemma 1, whenever R removes a positive term from $-B_m$, L can find a higher order negative term in the remaining sum to remove. Thus, $\{A \mid B\} - B_m + * - \uparrow(n) > 0$. □

Proposition 4: *If $A \geq 0$ is a sumner, B is a sumner with non-negative net weight and $X(A \mid B)$ is not empty, then $\{A \mid B\}$ is a sumner. Moreover $\{A \mid B\} = B_m + * + \uparrow(p)$ where m is the minimum cut of B and p is the simplest number in $X(A \mid B)$.*

Proof: To prove $\{A \mid B\} = B_m + * + \uparrow(p)$, it is sufficient to show that the first player cannot win the game $G = \{A \mid B\} - B_m + * - \uparrow(p)$.

Claim 1: L cannot win the game G .

L can choose terms from $\{A|B\}$, $-\uparrow(p)$, $-B_m$ or $*$. Since the later two are dominated options, we only need to consider the first two terms.

1. L cannot win G by choosing $\{A|B\}$, because, after L 's move, the remaining game will be $A - B_m + *-\uparrow(p) < | 0$ (because $p \in X(A|B)$).
2. L cannot win G by choosing $-\uparrow(p)$, because, after L 's move, the remaining game will be $\{A|B\} - B_m < | 0$ (because $B \leq B_m$).

In either case, L cannot win the game G .

Claim 2: R cannot win the game G .

R can choose terms from $\{A|B\}$, $-\uparrow(p)$, $-B_m$ or $*$.

1. R cannot win G by choosing $\{A|B\}$, because, after R 's move, the remaining game will be $B - B_m + *-\uparrow(p) > 0$ (because $p \in X(A|B)$).
2. If R chooses the $-\uparrow(p)$ term then the remaining game will be $\{A|B\} - B_m + *-\uparrow(p^L)$. Since p is the simplest number in $X(A|B)$, we have either $p^L \in X(A|B)$ or $p^L \notin X(A|B)$.
 - (a) If $p^L \notin X(A|B)$ then $A - B_m + *-\uparrow(p^L) \geq 0$, thus $\{A|B\} - B_m + *-\uparrow(p^L) > 0$.
 - (b) If $p^L \in X(A|B)$ then $p = m$, thus $\{A|B\} - B_m + *-\uparrow(p^L) = \{A|B\} - B_m + *-\uparrow(m^L) > 0$ (by lemma 3).
3. If R chooses a positive term, say $\uparrow(n)$, from $-B_m$ then L can respond a move at $-\uparrow(p)$. After the exchange, the remaining game becomes $\{A|B\} - B_m + *-\uparrow(n) > 0$ (by lemma 3). R should never consider choosing any negative terms from $-B_m$ because these options are dominated by the $-\uparrow(p)$ option.
4. If R chooses the $*$ term then L can respond a move at $-\uparrow(p)$. After the exchange, the remaining game becomes $\{A|B\} - B_m + * > 0$.

In any of the 4 cases, R cannot win the game G . □

Proposition 5: *If $A \geq 0$, $B || 0$ are sumbers, B has net weight -1 and $X(A|B)$ is not empty, then $\{A|B\} = B_m + *+\uparrow(p)$, where m is the minimum cut of B and p is the simplest number in $X(A|B)$.*

Proof: Since $B || 0$ and B 's net weight is -1 , we know the least order term in B is negative. Let $-\uparrow(q)$ be the least order term in B . Now, consider the sum $S = \{A+\uparrow(q)|B+\uparrow(q)\} - \uparrow(q) + \{-B|-A\}$. We want to show that the first player cannot win S .

By proposition 4, we know $\{A + \uparrow(q) | B + \uparrow(q)\} = B_m + \uparrow(q) + * + \uparrow(p)$, where m is the minimum cut of $B + \uparrow(q)$ and p is the simplest number in $X(A + \uparrow(q) | B + \uparrow(q))$. Note that the minimum cut of $B + \uparrow(q)$ equals the minimum cut of B and $X(A + \uparrow(q) | B + \uparrow(q)) = X(A | B)$. We can rewrite S as $S = B_m + \uparrow(q) + * + \uparrow(p) - \uparrow(q) + \{-B | -A\}$. Thus, $-\uparrow(q)$ is a dominated option for both players. If a player can win S , then the player must have a winning move other than $-\uparrow(q)$. Since neither of the players can win S by moving to $\{A + \uparrow(q) | B + \uparrow(q)\}$ or $\{-B | -A\}$, $S = 0$. Also note that the minimum cut if B equals the minimum cut of $B + \uparrow(q)$. We have $\{A | B\} = B_m + * + \uparrow(p)$, where m is the minimum cut of B and p is the simplest number in $X(A | B)$. \square

Proposition 6: *If $A > 0$ is a number with net weight 1, $B < 0$ is a number with net weight -1 , and $X(A | B)$ is not empty, then $\{A | B\}$ is a number. Moreover, if $A > *$ then $\{A | B\} = B_m + * + \uparrow(p)$, where m is the minimum cut of B and p is the simplest number in $X(A | B)$.*

Proof: Since $X(A | B)$ is not empty, we have either $A || *$ or $B || *$ (If $A > *$ and $B < *$ then $X(A | B)$ is empty.) If $A || *$ and $B || *$ then $\{A | B\} = *$. Otherwise, either $(A > *$ and $B || *)$ or $(A || *$ and $B < *)$. Without loss of generality, we may assume $A > *$ and $B || *$. Consider the sum $S = \{A + * | B + *\} + * + \{-B | -A\}$. We want to show that the first player cannot win S . Since $A + * > 0$, $B + *$ has net weight -1 and $B + * || 0$, by proposition 5, we have $\{A + * | B + *\} = B_m + \uparrow(p)$ where m is the minimum cut of B and p is the simplest number in $X(A | B)$. We can rewrite S as $S = B_m + \uparrow(p) + * + \{-B | -A\}$. Note that $*$ is a dominated option for both players. If a player can win S , then the player must have a winning move other than $*$. Since neither of the players can win S by moving to $\{A + * | B + *\}$ or $\{-B | -A\}$, we have $S = 0$. Thus, $\{A | B\} = B_m + * + \uparrow(p)$, where m is the minimum cut of B and p is the simplest number in $X(A | B)$. \square

4. Games with Multiple Options

Section 3 deals with games where each player has a unique option. In this section, we extend the theorem to deal with multiple-option games. Note that, sums of ups and downs (excluding $*$) are totally ordered. If G^L and G^R are sets of numbers, then G has at most two non-dominated options, one contains $*$ and the other does not, in each of G^L and G^R . In other words, G can be simplified as $G = \{A, B | C, D\}$ where A, B are the non-dominated options in G^L and C, D are the non-dominated options in G^R . Without loss of generality, we may assume the net weight of C is less than or equal to the net weight of D .

The critical section $X(G)$ of $G = \{A, B | C, D\}$ is defined as empty set, if C and D has the same net weight. Otherwise (the net weight of C is less than the net weight of D),

$X(G)$ is defined as the set of numbers $x \geq m$ satisfying all the following inequalities:

$$\uparrow(x) \mid > A - C_m + *,$$

$$\uparrow(x) \mid > B - C_m + *,$$

$$\uparrow(x) < \mid C - C_m + *,$$

$$\uparrow(x) < \mid D - C_m + *,$$

where m is the minimum cut of C .

Theorem 3: *Sumner simplification rule* (multi-option games).

Let $G = \{A, B \mid C, D\}$, where A, B, C and D are numbers. The net weight of C is less than or equal to the net weight of D .

1. If $A < \mid 0, B < \mid 0$ and $C \mid > 0, D \mid > 0$ then $G = 0$.
2. Otherwise, $A \geq 0, B \geq 0, C \leq 0$ or $D \leq 0$. Without loss of generality, we may assume $A \geq 0$ or $B \geq 0$ and the net weight of $A + C$ or $B + C$ is greater than or equal to 0 (otherwise, apply this rule to $-G$). By assumption, the net weight of C is greater than or equal to -1 .
 - (a) If C has non-negative net weight then G is a number if and only if $X(G)$ is not empty.
 - (b) If C has net weight -1 and $C \parallel 0$ then G is a number if and only if $X(G)$ is not empty.
 - (c) Otherwise, C has net weight -1 , and $C < 0$. If $A \parallel *, B \parallel *,$ and $C \parallel *, D \parallel *$ then $G = *$.
 - (d) Otherwise, C has net weight -1 , either $(A > * \text{ or } B > *)$ or $(C < * \text{ or } D < *)$. Without loss of generality, we may assume $A > * \text{ or } B > *$ (otherwise, apply this rule to $-G$). G is a number if and only if $X(G)$ is not empty.

In cases 2(a), 2(b), and 2(d), If G is a number then $G = C_m + * + \uparrow(p)$ where m is the minimum cut of C and p is the simplest number in $X(G)$.

The proofs for the above cases are similar to the ones provided in section 3.

5. Examples

Example 4: Consider the game $\{A \mid B\} = \{0 \mid \uparrow(1)\}$

The minimum cut of B occurs at 1. $B_1 = \uparrow(1)$ and $B^1 = 0$.

$$X(A \mid B) = \{x \geq 1 : A - B_1 + * < \mid \uparrow(x) < \mid B^1 + *\} = \{x \geq 1\}$$

The simplest number in $X(A|B)$ is 1.

By rule 2(a), we have $\{A|B\} = B_1 + * + \uparrow(1) = \uparrow(1) + \uparrow(1) + *$. □

Example 4 is the up-star equality first found by Conway[2]. Indeed, the equality still holds if 1 is replaced by any positive integer n .

$$\{0|\uparrow(n)\} = \uparrow(n) + \uparrow(n) + *.$$

When n is not an integer, the result is interesting.

Example 5: Consider the game $\{A|B\} = \{0|\uparrow(\frac{1}{2})\}$

The minimum cut of B occurs at $\frac{1}{2}$. $B_{\frac{1}{2}} = \uparrow(\frac{1}{2})$ and $B^{\frac{1}{2}} = 0$.

$$X(A|B) = \{x \geq \frac{1}{2} : A - B_{\frac{1}{2}} + * < |\uparrow(x) < |B^{\frac{1}{2}} + *\} = \{x \geq \frac{1}{2}\}$$

The simplest number in $X(A|B)$ is 1.

By rule 2(a), we have $\{A|B\} = B_{\frac{1}{2}} + * + \uparrow(1) = \uparrow(\frac{1}{2}) + \uparrow(1) + *$. □

There are cases where A and B are numbers with term(s) of integer order(s), but $\{A|B\}$ is a number with term(s) of non-integer order(s).

Example 6: Consider the game $\{A|B\} = \{\uparrow(1)|* + 2.\uparrow(2) - 2.\uparrow(3)\}$

The minimum cut of B occurs at 0. $B_0 = *$ and $B^0 = 2.\uparrow(2) - 2.\uparrow(3)$.

$$X(A|B) = \{x \geq 0 : A - B_0 + * < |\uparrow(x) < |B^0 + *\} = \{1 < x < 2\}$$

The simplest number in $X(A|B)$ greater than or equal to 0 is $1\frac{1}{2}$.

By rule 2(a), we have $\{A|B\} = B_0 + * + \uparrow(1\frac{1}{2}) = \uparrow(1\frac{1}{2})$. □

There are cases where A and B are numbers, but $\{A|B\}$ is not a number. In general, if $A - B > \uparrow(n) + *$, for any n , then $\{A|B\}$ is not a number.

Example 7: Consider the game $\{A|B\} = \{\uparrow(1) + \uparrow(1)|*\}$

The minimum cut of B occurs at 0. $B_0 = *$ and $B^0 = 0$.

$$X(G) = \{x \geq 0 : A - B_0 + * < |\uparrow(x) < |B^0 + *\} = \{\}$$

$X(A|B)$ is an empty set, so $\{A|B\}$ is not a number. □

There are cases where all the games in G^L and G^R are numbers, the difference between G^L and G^R is less than $\uparrow(n) + *$ for some n , but G is not a number.

Example 8: Consider the game $G = \{A|B, C\} = \{\uparrow(1)|*, \uparrow(1)\}$

The minimum cut of B occurs at 0. $B_0 = *$ and $B^0 = 0$.

$$X(G) = \{x \geq 0 : A - B_0 + * < |\uparrow(x) < |B^0 + * \text{ and } \uparrow(x) < |C - B_0 + *\} = \{\}$$

$X(G)$ is an empty set, so G is not a number. □

6. Conclusion

This article introduces a subgroup of games called *sumber*s. Similar to numbers and nimbers, sumber have the following properties:

1. Sumber are closed under addition.
2. There exists a simple rule to determine the outcome of a sumber.
3. There exists a simplification rule that can, when G is a sumber, determine the exact sumber of G from G^L and G^R .

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